

Research

Empirical study on the comparison of Regional competitiveness of Asian Countries in perspective of Global Competitiveness Index

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Abstract: This study examines the hierarchical level of competitiveness in Asian countries using 12 global competitive development indicators. We applied multivariate analysis- Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA) and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to distinguish the clusters combination in 33 Asian economies. The research has identified two principal components responsible for 78% variations of the indicators in the data sets. And the countries have been classified into four clusters- A, B, C and D with some sub-clusters. The result proves that economies like Singapore, Japan, S. Korea, Qatar, Malaysia, Israel and UAE are on the top of hierarchy where Cyprus and Bahrain are in the 2nd cluster, while the rest are in 3rd & fourth cluster. The analysis showed infrastructure (INFRT 0.950), business sophistication (BS 0.926), & goods market efficiency (GME 0.920) have the highest impact on Asian development while the other are also contributing. Most of the development indicators kept very close connection to PC1 while only two- macroeconomic environment (MEE) and market size (MS) are close to PC2. So, this research mainly emphasizes on the hierarchical classification of the countries and sort out the main component influencing the development trend in Asia. Furthermore, it will help policy makers and investors to emphasize on the facts those have direct influence on sustainable Asian development policy as well.

Keywords: global competitiveness; hierarchical cluster analysis; principal component analysis; sustainable development; Asian economy.

1 Introduction

Sustainable development for the countries to challenge the world crisis in recent years is very important specially to amend Asian fragmented economy. Green industry, technology, logistics

& green economy are clear indications towards regional development. Changes in the global market situation have revealed serious disproportions in economic stability and the ability of national economies, the competitiveness of which are not uniform and represent the main driving force of recent macroeconomic imbalances, to recover quickly (Bucher, 2018). Industrialization & sustainable development continues to be the main driving forces for global competitiveness. With productivity, the most important determinants of long-term growth, income, & sustainable development are the new global competitiveness (Schwab, 2019). Enhancing the fundamentals of competitiveness today will improve resilience to shocks. Building economic resilience through competitiveness is more important (Schwab, 2019). We need to arrive at reconciliation between the desire for economic and social development on the one hand, and environmental protection on the other (Filho et al., 2017). Competitiveness, equality and sustainability in whole region of the world aren't same. Inequality of opportunity, inequality of income and economic growth form a circular nexus (Schwab, 2019). Climate change is already affecting hundreds of millions around the world. Developing economies in Asia suffers a lot from these.

The Global Competitiveness Index (GCI) has been measuring the factors that drive long-term growth and prosperity for over four decades, helping policymakers identify challenges to be addressed and strengths to build on when designing the economic growth strategies for their countries (Schwab, 2017). Globalization has increased inequality within countries by transferring low-skilled jobs in high-productivity sectors from advanced economies to developing and emerging countries (Schwab, 2019). Fragmented Asia in terms of health, education, technology, infrastructure, innovation and market efficiency has shown remarkable development but it has lagged behind in comparison of global competitiveness indicators score. So, this study has attempted to cluster the economies according to the hierarchies and reveal the importance level of the development indicators for sustainable Asian development. Figure 1 shows the global competitive development indicators.

Figure 1: Global competitiveness indicators towards sustainable development

Achieving equality, sustainability and growth together is possible in Asian countries but needs proactive development of labor market efficiency, technological, health education & training, protection of environment and development of infrastructure. We are observing a mixed performance of competitiveness in G20 & BRICS (Schwab, 2018), other countries have very different results on social and environmental factors for the same level of current competitiveness (Schwab, 2019), while Asian economies are demonstrating lower performance towards sustainability. Institutes—including security, property rights, social capital, checks and balances, transparency and ethics, public-sector performance and corporate governance (Schwab, 2019) are very curtail for the development. But weak institutions continue to hamper competitiveness, development and well-being in many countries (Schwab, 2019). The promise of leveraging technology & innovation for economic leapfrogging is very essential. Innovation has become an imperative for all emerging Asian economics. But use of technology—has not kept up with the pace of innovation in most countries (Schwab, 2019) while openness is good for sustainable growth, more open economies are more innovative and their markets more competitive. Countries must improve talent adaptability; that is, enable the ability of their workforces. Talent adaptability also requires a well functioning labor market that protects workers rather than jobs (Manta, 2019; Schwab, 2018, 2019). It is possible for an economy to be growing, inclusive and environmentally sustainable—but few economies are on such a trajectory (Schwab, 2019). The efficient movement of people, goods, services and information is a prerequisite for competitiveness, as well as access to adequate quantity and quality of markets and resources, including finance (Manta, 2019). The movement of workers from agriculture to manufacturing to services has been the path of structural transformation in all economies that

comprise the high-income club as well as the pattern of successful growth in East Asia(Sawada & Yoshino, 2019).

To best of our knowledge, no research has yet been done on clustering the Asian economies in different hierarchies according to the global competitiveness and show the level of significance of the competitive indicators. So, this study is conducted to clarify the level of development in Asia & make a cluster of the development indicators to signify their importance for sustainable Asia in terms of technology, innovation, infrastructure, health & education, business sophistication, market development and efficiency. And this study further will contribute helping policymakers identify challenges to be addressed and strengths to take decision where to put more effort and investment for reviving productivity growth.

The remainder of this study is structured as- section 2 provides a brief of related literature review, data extraction and econometric methodology have been narrated in section 3, result analysis is in section 4, discussions in section 5 and final section 6- is conclusion.

2 Related literature reviews

Most of the previous researches on competitiveness are based on the individual economy and all of them have tried to sort out the level of development of a particular country, region or a group. Very few researches have been done on the level of importance of the global competitive indicators clustering them into different level in accordance with their hierarchies. Our study has tried to mend this gap for Asian economy to cluster the development indicators easily for sustainable development.

Mao, Y., Liu, K. and Zhou, J (Mao et al., 2019), have evaluated industry level development of China and Europe using hierarchical cluster analysis to see the improvement of sustainable development by industry. They have concluded that consumption of renewable energy is increasing & the result is the decrease of GHG for sustainable development. Huggins, R., Izushi, H., Prokop, D. and Thompson, P (Huggins et al., 2014), showed theoretical notion & empirical attention of the global competitiveness of regions for quantifying the rapid sustainability of each region. Bowen, H. and Moesen, W (Bowen & Moesen, 2011) inspired by data envelopment analysis (DEA) endogenously determined country specific weights using aggregation methodology to trace the development level of individual economy. However, Hasan, Hasan & Nishi, (Hasan, 2017; Hasan & Nishi, 2019) showed the economic and sustainable development in their empirical study using linear model.

The role of higher education and training for sustainable development is shown by Utama Y (Utama et al., 2018), while competitive sustainable development indicators like- environmental degradation & over exploitation of natural resources, technological development & business sophistication, and market growth have been given more importance for achieving a better global performance and business for sustainable development by Chaiprasit et al., Ozdemirci et al., and Galgánková, V (Chaiprasit & Swierczek, 2011; Galgánková, 2020; Ozdemirci et al., 2019).

Applying global multi-criteria indices on the assessment of the interrelation of business environment, human development, and sustainable growth, Kiseľáková et al., have analyzed linear relation of GCI and HDI for sustainability in their study (Kiseľáková et al., 2019). Fifeková et al., have used data envelopment analysis (DEA) to analyze the GCI sustainable development indicators and found the efficiency of transformation of competitiveness into economic performance. A robustness of inefficiency and indicate common patterns of development for some country groups has been detected in their study (Fifeková et al., 2019).

Workie et al., have checked the cross-positive effect across global competitiveness indicators and have come out with result of positive cross-effects between sub-indices for a group of economies in the European Union (EU) and other certain advanced economies. Economies with an advanced level of higher education and training, and a superior level of innovation, tend to experience a higher level of ranking in the global competitiveness index compared to countries with lower levels of education and innovation (Workie & Hekelová, 2016). Lall S (Lall, 2001), analyzed development competitiveness if it is legitimate concern and found deficiencies of sustainability at several levels in developing countries.

3 Data & research methodologies

3.1 Data collection & stability test

Data on 33 Asian countries (Appendix A) have been collected in this research. Data are collected from global competitiveness report published by World Economic Forum (WEF). 12 global competitive indicators namely institutions, infrastructure, macroeconomic environment, health & primary education, higher education & training, goods market efficiency, labor market efficiency, financial market development, technological readiness, market size, business sophistication & innovation have been defined by the WEF to measure the development competitiveness. All indicators are measured on a scale of 1 low-7 high. Indicators' list & descriptive statistics of the indicators have been shows in table (1) & table (2) respectively.

Table 1: Indicators with abbreviation chosen for the study.

Indicators	Abbreviation	Data Source
Institutions	INST	WCR
Infrastructure	INFRT	WCR
Macroeconomic environment	MEE	WCR
Health and primary education	HPEDU	WCR
Higher education and training	HEDUT	WCR
Goods market efficiency	GME	WCR
Labor market efficiency	LME	WCR
Financial market development	FMD	WCR
Technological readiness	TR	WCR
Market size	MS	WCR
Business sophistication	BS	WCR
Innovation	INV	WCR

WCR: World Competitiveness Report by WEF

Descriptive statistics presented in the table (2) shows a positive mean value & a substantial peak of the distribution which indicates the strong association and correlation of the indicators in Asian countries. No doubt that greater and positive mean value implies the strong relation among the variables.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of the indicators

Indicators	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max	Cronbach's α level
INST	4.201515	0.7915382	2.9	6.2	0.92
INFRT	4.180606	1.127328	1.8	6.5	
MEE	4.985455	0.9514829	2.6	6.7	
HPEDU	5.673182	0.5670945	3.2	6.9	
HEDUT	4.256061	0.7524487	2.5	6.3	
GME	4.461515	0.4964348	3.5	5.8	
LME	4.402424	0.5087623	3.3	5.9	
FMD	4.214242	0.6271542	3	5.9	
TR	3.927879	0.9530682	2.2	6.2	
MS	4.233939	1.170691	2.2	7	
BS	4.177273	0.6598322	2.8	5.9	
INV	3.546061	0.8233298	2	5.8	

N. Obs.: Number of observations 33

Besides, we have checked Pearson correlation 2-tailed (Table 3) along with overall Cronbach's alpha (α) level (Cronbach's alpha test, 1951) presented in the table (2) to check the reliability & stability of the data. The test has been done to present data validation & internal consistency among the variables. Cronbach's Alpha (α) level is a consistency. The acceptance level is $\alpha > 0.6$. 0.7 as suggested by Nunnally (1978) & $0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$ recommended by Wikipedia. The overall Cronbach's Alpha level we got is 0.92 that is definitely greater than the recommended level. It indicates the internal consistency of the variables we used in the research (Garver & Mentzer, 1999).

Table 3: Pearson correlation (2-tailed) of the indicators

Indicators	INST	INFRT	MEE	HPEDU	HEDUT	GME	LME	FMD	TR	MS	BS	INV
INST	1											
INFRT	0.827** 0.000	1										
MEE	0.190 0.290	0.397* 0.022	1									
HPEDU	0.658** 0.000	0.729** 0.000	0.238 0.181	1								
HEDUT	0.690** 0.000	0.846** 0.000	0.314 0.075	0.802** 0.000	1							
GME	0.871** 0.000	0.885** 0.000	0.304 0.085	0.699** 0.000	0.746** 0.000	1						
LME	0.724** 0.000	0.639** 0.000	0.207 0.247	0.668** 0.000	0.650** 0.000	0.757** 0.000	1					
FMD	0.761** 0.000	0.660** 0.000	0.460** 0.007	0.484** 0.004	0.513** 0.002	0.729** 0.000	0.582** 0.000	1				
TR	0.728** 0.000	0.905** 0.000	0.281 0.114	0.725** 0.000	0.837** 0.000	0.811** 0.000	0.692** 0.000	0.550** 0.001	1			
MS	0.194 0.280	0.423* 0.014	0.494** 0.004	0.064 0.723	0.302 0.088	0.157 0.382	.003 0.987	0.341 0.052	0.170 0.345	1		

BS	0.811**	0.882**	0.383*	0.602**	0.728**	0.838**	0.592**	0.801**	0.735**	0.490**	1	
	0.000	0.000	0.028	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.004		
INV	0.750**	0.811**	0.359*	0.589**	0.742**	0.760**	0.643**	0.754**	0.722**	0.457**	0.936**	1
	0.000	0.000	0.040	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.007	0.000	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Q-Q plot (Appendix B) presents the validity result of the normal distribution. It's just a visual check, not an air-tight proof, so it is somewhat subjective. But it allows us to see at-a-glance if our assumption is plausible, and if not (University of Virginia Library).

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) statistics & Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is presented in the Table 4. KMO is used for assessing sampling adequacy and evaluates the correlations and partial correlations to determine if the data are likely to coalesce on components. KMO statistic should be greater than 0.600 and the Bartlett's test should be significant (e.g. $p < .05$) to use principal component analysis. KMO statistics we got here is 0.784 that is greater than 0.60 and the Bartlett's test of sphericity is 0.000 which is statistically significant (5% significant level). So from the above results we know that we can now continue and perform a valid factor analysis.

Table 4: Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.784
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	440.961
	df	66
	Sig.	.000

3.2 Methodology

3.2.1 Hierarchical cluster Analysis (HCA)

Hierarchical cluster Analysis (HCA) is a technique for performing data exploratory analysis to cluster them into different group or cluster (Mao et al., 2019; Nielsen, 2016). HCA aims to divide and discriminate the data matrix into different hierarchies. The initial sequence is random and disordered (Mao et al., 2019). It finds relatively homogeneous clusters of cases based on measured characteristics (Jiang & Chen, 2009). Conceptual HCA plot on the indicators of global competitiveness indicators is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Plot of the theory of Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (merge tree).

There two strategies of HCA- agglomerative hierarchical clustering & divisive hierarchical clustering. Hierarchical clustering consists in building a binary merge tree, starting from the data elements stored at the leaves and proceed by merging two by two the “closest” sub-sets until we reach the root of the tree that contains all the elements of X (Nielsen, 2016). The distance, called linkage distance, between any two sub-sets (X_i, X_j) of X is denoted by Δ . This technique is also called agglomerative hierarchical clustering as we start from the leaves storing singletons & merge iteratively subsets until the expected cluster number is obtained (Jiang & Chen, 2009; Milligan & Cooper, 1986; Nielsen, 2016; Wetherell, 1977). Agglomerative hierarchical clustering generates a dendrogram tree that represents the entire data sets. The height of the dendrogram usually expresses the distance between each pair of data objects or clusters, or a data object and a cluster (Jiang & Chen, 2009). The statistical distances between the data points were evaluated. Two data points were merged into a new cluster according to the minimum distance (Mao et al., 2019). The graphical representation of this binary merge tree is called a dendrogram. Visual drawing of hierarchical dendrogram, conveys information for both qualitative and quantitative evaluations of cluster (Nielsen, 2016).

In order to get the component score we need to obtain component score coefficient and value of the standardized indicator. The value of standardization can be obtained from the equation written as

$$Z_{ij} = \frac{X_{ij} - \bar{X}_{ij}}{\sigma_j} \quad (5)$$

Here Z_{ij} denotes standardized value of the j^{th} observations and i^{th} variables, \bar{X}_{ij} is the average of j^{th} observations and i^{th} variables and σ_j standard deviation of the data sets where

$$\bar{X}_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n X_i}{n}, \quad (6)$$

And
$$\sigma_j = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (X_{ij} - \bar{X}_j)^2} \quad (7)$$

And the coefficient of principal component can be derived from

$$\sum_{i=1}^p a_{ij}^2 = a_j a_j = 1 \quad (8)$$

If we consider that the sample variance-covariance matrix of the original variables, X is S_x , then the coefficient vector, a_j , can be obtained from this equations:

$$|S_x - \lambda I| a = 0 \quad (9)$$

Here, λ is the vector of characteristic roots and 'a' is a matrix comprising of the characteristic vectors corresponding to each characteristic root. The equation to obtain PC score is

$$PCS = FC \times Z \quad (10)$$

Where $PCS = PCS_1$ and PCS_2 is the score of each country and $Z = Z_1, Z_2, Z_3, Z_4, \dots, Z_{12}$. is the standardized variable and FC is the factor coefficient might be obtained after data analysis.

On basis of equation (10) and the contribution rate of factor variance as weights calculated from eigenvalues average we further may calculate the comprehensive scores (CS) of each country to rank them, the calculation equation is

$$CS = W_i \times PCS_1 + W_i \times PCS_2 \quad (11)$$

Here $W_i = W_1, W_2$ is the weight of each factor which is obtained from $W_i = \frac{\lambda_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i}$ and λ_i is the extracted eigenvalues.

The great advantage of multivariate (PCA) method other than conventional econometric is driven when the explanatory of the equation to be adjusted made significant autocorrelation. So, the variables obtained from PCA are orthogonal & present zero correlation (Beaumont, 2012; Carvalho & Fonseca, 2017).

4 Result & discussion

To distinguish the importance level of the global competitiveness in Asia, figure 3 illustrates the result of HCA from a dendrogram tree. 33 Asian countries have been considered within competitiveness as the global development criterion towards sustainability in the 21st century. Countries are figured out into four clusters with distance cluster combine & ranked in accordance with their component scores (Table 8).

According to the figure 3, Singapore, S. Korea, Japan, Qatar, Malaysia, Israel & UAE are located in the 1st cluster of the dendrogram (A). It's because of the best infrastructure, business sophistication, higher education & training, technological readiness and innovation, these economies are doing well in Asia with high values. Cyprus & Bahrain are grouped in 2nd cluster (B) while China, India, Turkey, Russia, Thailand, Indonesia, Philippines, Kuwait, S. Arabia, and Oman are in 3rd cluster (C). Bangladesh, Pakistan, Nepal, Azerbaijan, Armenia, Tajikistan, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Vietnam, Sri Lanka and Nepal are in D, 4th cluster for their low macroeconomic stability with low facilities of health & primary education and business environment. Cluster C is divided into two sub-group E and F. China and India are in same sub-cluster while Turkey, Russia, Thailand, Indonesia and Philippines with other Arab countries are in sub-cluster F. Cluster D broke down into two sub-cluster; G with Bangladesh & Pakistan, while Sri Lanka, Vietnam, Nepal & some other central Asian countries are classified in sub-cluster H for fragmented infrastructure, less growth rate and inefficient financial market development.

Singapore, Japan, Qatar, Israel & UAE are in one cluster with rescaled distance cluster combine between 19 and 25, that is the indications of high economic impact for sustainable development in the region. Financial market development enables countries to access more distant financial markets in Asia. Consequently, external funds become cheaper and easier to access, which spurs capital accumulation and economic growth (Boukhatem et al., 2020). Financial market development & integration contributes to macroeconomic stability through positive effect on output growth, improving risk sharing and smoothing opportunities as well as increasing efficiency in resource allocation and market liquidity (Bonga-Bonga, 2017; Boukhatem et al., 2020). Chinese innovation and Indian raising technology farms development have clustered them close together.

Figure 3: Hierarchical Cluster Dendrogram of the Asian countries

It's clear from the hierarchical cluster analysis that developed economies in Asia are doing well while less developing & less privileged economies are lagged behind towards SDGs. Although the rise in FDI inflow to developing economies pushed up from 18% in 2016 to 20% in 2017 and from 31% to 34% in East and South-East Asia (ADB, 2018) . Singapore remained the region's largest recipient, accounting for 45 per cent of total FDI in ASEAN(ADB, 2018). This may be the reason for Singapore to develop institutions, infrastructure and goods market efficiency & stand on the top of the ranking. However, MNEs such as Aeon (Japan), Ayala (Philippines), Seven-Eleven (Japan), Alibaba (China) and ASEAN companies such as Axiata (Malaysia), RedDoorz (Singapore), San Miguel (Philippines), Maybank (Malaysia), Keppel (Singapore), and Siam Cement (Thailand) expanded in Asia (ADB, 2018).

Result of PCA has been presented in table 5. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is perfect for removing multi-colinearity because it maximizes the variance rather than minimizing the least square distance where any other technique (such as regression analysis) fails to do so (Jiang & Chen, 2009). Eigen values greater than 1 criteria (Eigenvales> 1) extracted PCs shown in the table 5 that there are two components. It is further confirmed by the scree plot (figure 4). Scree plot proves the break point of the components.

Figure 4: scree plot of Eigenvalues for components confirmation

Component loadings are presented in table 6. Infrastructure (INFRT), Goods market efficiency (GME) and Business sophistications (BS) are on the top with high factor loadings. However, the value of factor loadings of other indicators are also high except Macroeconomic environment (MEE) and Market size (MS) and the reason for it is the low correlation got from Pearson correlation of the variables.

Table 5: Eigen values of the correlation matrix

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	7.871	65.593	65.593	7.871	65.593	65.593
2	1.505	12.541	78.134	1.505	12.541	78.134
3	.721	6.006	84.141			
4	.650	5.418	89.559			
5	.326	2.713	92.271			
6	.291	2.427	94.698			
7	.234	1.948	96.646			

8	.139	1.156	97.801
9	.124	1.036	98.836
10	.096	.798	99.635
11	.028	.028	99.870
12	.016	.130	100.000

The analysis showed that the cumulative contribution of 12 indicators was 100%. Two principal components together can explain 78% (65.5%+12.5%) of the total variance in the data sets where first PCs analyze 64% of the total variations alone. The communalities values shown in the (appendix C) which are the total influence on a single observed variable from all the factors associated with it (Beaumont, 2012). It is equal to the sum of all the squared factor loadings for all the factors related to the observed variable and this value is the same as R^2 in multiple regressions(Beaumont, 2012). The value ranges from zero to 1 where 1 indicates that the variable can be fully defined by the factors and has no uniqueness. In contrast a value of 0 indicates that the variable cannot be predicted at all from any of the factors(Beaumont, 2012).

Table 6. Component loadings (Eigenvectors)

	Component	
	PC1	PC2
INST	.885	-.171
INFRT	.950	.039
MEE	.424	.638
HPEDU	.780	-.308
HEDUT	.867	-.100
GME	.920	-.171
LME	.773	-.384
FMD	.796	.196
TR	.879	-.195
MS	.368	.823
BS	.926	.184
INV	.896	.156

According to equation 10, the calculated PCs scores obtained to ranking the countries displayed in table 7. From the table it is clear that countries with high economy, growth rate, business sophistication and infrastructure are getting better & better.

Table 7: Ranking of 33 Asian economies in terms of global competitiveness indicators

Name of the economy	PC1 score	PC1 ranking	PC2 score	PC2 ranking
Singapore	2.532	1	-0.465	23
Japan	1.779	2	-0.013	18
UAE	1.721	3	-0.215	20
Israel	1.489	4	-0.128	19
Qatar	1.340	5	0.002	16
Malaysia	1.168	6	0.368	12
S. Korea	0.990	7	1.222	5
Bahrain	0.590	8	-1.671	32
China	0.464	9	1.662	1
S. Arabia	0.418	10	0.302	13

Cyprus	0.153	11	-1.827	33
Thailand	0.123	12	1.280	3
Indonesia	0.085	13	1.607	2
Oman	-0.035	14	-0.324	22
India	-0.100	15	1.235	4
Russia	-0.127	16	0.521	11
Jordan	-0.247	17	-0.845	26
Armenia	-0.313	18	-1.477	30
Azerbaijan	-0.313	19	-1.477	31
Turkey	-0.349	20	0.952	8
Kazakhstan	-0.414	21	-0.859	27
Georgia	-0.415	22	-0.724	24
Philippines	-0.513	23	1.198	6
Kuwait	-0.528	24	0.793	10
Vietnam	-0.546	25	0.109	15
Tajikistan	-0.646	26	-1.319	29
S. Lanka	-0.702	27	-0.009	17
Mongolia	-1.081	28	-1.107	28
Cambodia	-1.122	29	-0.268	21
Kyrgyzstan	-1.210	30	-0.759	25
Nepal	-1.216	31	0.274	14
Bangladesh	-1.383	32	0.864	9
Pakistan	-1.587	33	1.097	7

Figure 5 testifies that most of the competitiveness indicators are close to the PC1 with producing high values for the variations in the development process in Asian countries.

Figure 5: Component plot of factor 1 & 2

5 Discussions and conclusions

For this study of global competitiveness indicators and cluster combination in Asian economy, hierarchical cluster analysis & principal component analysis were developed. The contribution of this research is the identification of factors & clustering of the countries in order to implement the strategies and policies in accordance with extracted results.

According to the result of the analysis, clusters are summarized in table 8 and a cluster map of Asia is presented in figure 6. HCA confirms that Asian sustainable development is revolving round only some developed countries. Development process is centered now. Developing & under developing economies like Pakistan, Bangladesh, Nepal, Mongolia, Kyrgyzstan, Sri Lanka, Vietnam, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Georgia, Jordan, Azerbaijan, Armenia should give more opportunities to ensure sustainability. Infrastructure like- upgrading bridges, roads, railway lines, airports and power plants; education-training; economic activities-e-commerce & business sophistication must give priority.

Health & education with training are considered as the prerequisite of productivity. South Asia also lags behind not only in terms of transport infrastructure (SDGs 9) but also in basic needs such as access to sanitation (SDGs 6) and access to electricity (SDGs 7)(Kumar et al., 2016). The result of components analysis shows that all the development indicators accept Asian macroeconomic stability and market size are impacting the regional sustainability. As macroeconomic indicators don't derive economic growth but it's necessary to promote productivity. The global competitiveness indicators shown in component plot of factors 1 & 2 (figure 5) indicate the combined influence of the factors.

Table 8: Cluster category of the economies

Cluster	Economies	Category
First	Singapore, Japan, Qatar, Israel, S. Korea, Malaysia, UAE	A-high clustered
Second	Bahrain & Cyprus	B-middle clustered
Third	India, China, Turkey, Russia, Thailand, Indonesia, Philippines, Kuwait, S. Arabia, Oman,	C- lower clustered
Fourth	Pakistan, Bangladesh, Nepal, Cambodia, Mongolia, Kyrgyzstan, Sri Lanka, Vietnam, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Georgia, Jordan, Azerbaijan, Armenia	D-tertiary cluster

Figure 6: Different clusters counters in Asia

This study shows the level of hierarchy of the economies and the most influential competitive indicators impacting global development. The contribution of this study is that it will create an evaluation scale for the policy makers where to emphasize in Asia. The 17 sustainable development goals accepted by 193 economies of the world encompassing three core dimensions of economic, social and environmental development. The development priority has been given in Asia to recover the development gaps among the economies. Though Asian economies have achieved the MDGs including poverty reduction, in terms on innovation, infrastructure, higher education-training, financial market development and technological readiness, most parts of the region are struggling to compete of sustainability.

Some recommendations towards regional competitiveness for sustainable development of Asian countries are-

- 1 Asian country should expand their market size as emerging markets provide excellent opportunities both in terms of overall growth rates and in response to rapidly changing market trends.
- 2 Macroeconomic indicators should give more care to increasing the share of industry in GDP and doubling it for LDCs is particularly relevant for South Asia for its potential to create decent productivity and foster economic growth(Kumar et al., 2016).
- 3 Investments needs for developed & stable financial market as it improves the allocation of capital to entrepreneurs and investment opportunities by enabling investors to find information about investment opportunities that have the best chance of improving sustainability.
- 4 Asian countries with limited natural resources should be more innovative as innovation is no longer the reserve of wealthy countries. Asian countries may have look on contemporary Singapore & Israel for innovative activities. Innovation facilities and higher education & training

in Asia are urgent as flows of investment in developing Asia remained stable, at \$476 billion in 2018 (Kiprop, 2020; UNCTAD, 2018).

6 Privatization has already helped fire up China's economic growth and other countries like Turkey are also looking to benefit from increased efficiency and better access to capital. Others should follow them to increase the possibility of sustainable development (Ruske et al., 2010).

7 Countries with efficient labor market promote productivity. Greater labor market flexibility also increases the ability of a country to reallocate production to emerging segments and adapt the workforce to the new needs of high-tech sectors.

8 Big economies should come forward extending their hands to equilibrium the development level.

9 Finally, Asian countries can build up different regional development hub like SAARC, BIMSTEC, SEAGA and ADB to cooperate and extend their mutual assistance for sustainability.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of financial interest regarding this research.

Appendix A: Country list

1	Armenia	12	Japan	23	Qatar
2	Azerbaijan	13	Jordan	24	Russia
3	Bahrain	14	Kazakhstan	25	Saudi Arabia
4	Bangladesh	15	Kuwait	26	Singapore
5	Cambodia	16	Kyrgyzstan	27	South Korea
6	China	17	Malaysia	28	Sri Lanka
7	Cyprus	18	Mongolia	29	Tajikistan
8	Georgia	19	Nepal	30	Thailand
9	India	20	Oman	31	Turkey
10	Indonesia	21	Pakistan	32	United Arab Emirates (UAE)
11	Israel	22	Philippines	33	Vietnam

Appendix B: QQ plot of indicators

QQ plot- MEE

QQ plot- HPEDU

QQ plot- HEDUT

QQ plot- GME

QQ plot- LME

QQ plot- FMD

QQ plot- TR

QQ plot-MS

QQ plot- BS

QQ plot- INV

Appendix C: Communalities extracted from PCA

	Communalities	
	Initial	Extraction
INST	1.000	.851
INFRT	1.000	.894
MEE	1.000	.248
HPEDU	1.000	.668
HEDUT	1.000	.790
GME	1.000	.858
LME	1.000	.644
FMD	1.000	.617
TR	1.000	.833
MS	1.000	.892
BS	1.000	.876
INV	1.000	.807

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

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